

Enhancing Educational and Social Support for Orphaned Children: A Case Study of SOS Children's Village Faisalabad

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ABSTRACT:

Orphaned children represent a vulnerable segment of society, often deprived of essential support systems necessary for their holistic development. In response to this pressing need, institutions such as SOS Children's Village Faisalabad have emerged as beacons of hope, providing comprehensive educational and social support to orphaned children. This study explores the role of SOS Children's Village Faisalabad in enhancing educational and social support for orphaned children through a case study approach. The study employs a mixed-method research design, combining quantitative and qualitative methodologies to gather comprehensive insights into the educational and social support programs implemented by SOS Children's Village Faisalabad. Data were collected from orphaned children residing in the village, as well as teachers and staff members involved in program implementation. Key findings reveal that SOS Children's Village Faisalabad offers a range of educational support programs, including formal schooling facilities, tutoring services, vocational training, and extracurricular activities. These programs are designed to meet the diverse needs and aspirations of orphaned children, empowering them with knowledge, skills, and confidence for future success. Additionally, the institution places a strong emphasis on fostering social integration and emotional well-being among orphaned children through mentorship programs, counseling services, recreational activities, and community engagement initiatives. These efforts aim to create a supportive and nurturing environment where children can thrive socially and emotionally. The study highlights the transformative impact of SOS Children's Village Faisalabad on the lives of orphaned children, as evidenced by success stories of academic achievement, personal growth, and community integration. Furthermore, it underscores the broader implications of the institution's model for orphan care and support programs globally, emphasizing the importance of holistic approaches that prioritize education, support, and empowerment. Based on the findings, recommendations are provided for policymakers, NGOs, and other stakeholders to further enhance educational and social support for orphaned children, including investment in education, holistic support services, community engagement, training and capacity building, and research and evaluation. In conclusion, SOS Children's Village Faisalabad serves as a shining example of the transformative power of dedicated care and support in the lives of orphaned children, offering hope, opportunity, and a brighter future for vulnerable youth in the region and beyond.

KEYWORDS: Orphaned children, SOS Children's Village Faisalabad, Educational support, Social integration, vulnerable youth

1. INTRODUCTION:

Orphaned children represent one of the most vulnerable groups in society, facing numerous challenges that hinder their access to education and social support. The order should offer them adequate opportunities for their straitlaced employment and education. After state, it is the primary responsibility of parents and family of a child. (Abro, 2012). In many cases, they lack the essential familial and community structures necessary for their holistic development. Recognizing this critical need, organizations such as SOS Children's Village Faisalabad have emerged as beacons of hope, providing a nurturing environment where orphaned children can thrive academically, socially, and emotionally. Education is real important factor in human life,

because if you get the knowledge about certain thing, you will be able make a better decision (Abraham, et al 2004). Children are brought to the orphanage home for one of three reasons: First, the parents have abandoned them. Second, the parents have had their parental rights removed by the state because they are in prison, are drug abusers, or abused the child and thirds, the child who has parents died (Lowdermilk and Perry, 2004).

In the bustling district of Faisalabad, Pakistan, where the orphan crisis is a poignant reality, SOS Children's Village stands as a testament to the power of compassionate intervention. The SOS is supporting many programs like educational institutions, management of health care centers and street child's care (Akram, et.al 2015). Founded with the mission of restoring the dignity and future prospects of orphaned children, this institution has become a cornerstone of support for the community. Through its comprehensive educational and social support programs, SOS Children's Village Faisalabad endeavors to uplift the lives of orphaned children, offering them a second chance at a brighter tomorrow. It becomes very threatening for many families to chance up with the learning and medical expenditures. That's why they are bound to involve their families to produce money for their living (Ali, 2011). SOS Children's Village Faisalabad was founded in 1988 in which the land was donated by the Government of Punjab along with many local humanitarians funded the family homes. Faisalabad (formerly known as Lyallpur) is a city in the province of Punjab and is the third largest city in Pakistan after Karachi and Lahore (SOS Children's Villages Faisalabad). The SOS Village Faisalabad has been an immensely successful project with over 147 orphans and abandoned children being cared for and 283 children studying in the SOS school (Feb 2017).

This study delves into the multifaceted efforts of SOS Children's Village Faisalabad to enhance educational and social support for orphaned children. By examining the institution's programs, methodologies, and impact, we aim to shed light on the transformative potential of dedicated care and intervention in the lives of vulnerable youth. The child's overall development, especially academic and social outcome is influenced by these emotional and behavioral difficulties as adults. Therefore, there is a need for assessment and identification of mental health problems in these institutionalized children so that appropriate intervention actions can be

planned for them at the right time. (Musisi S, 2007). Through a combination of empirical research, anecdotal evidence, and firsthand accounts, we explore the holistic approach adopted by SOS Children's Village Faisalabad, emphasizing its role as a catalyst for positive change in the lives of orphaned children. Moreover, it is imperative to underscore the significance of our inquiry. Beyond the confines of Faisalabad, the lessons gleaned from this case study hold relevance for orphan care initiatives worldwide. By dissecting the successes, challenges, and best practices of SOS Children's Village Faisalabad, we aim to contribute to the broader discourse on orphan care, fostering dialogue, innovation, and ultimately, greater opportunities for vulnerable children everywhere.

1.1. Background and Context:

The city of Faisalabad, nestled in the heart of Pakistan, pulsates with life and commerce. Yet, amidst the bustling streets and vibrant markets, there exists a stark reality: a significant population of orphaned children grappling with the harsh realities of life without familial support. Economic hardships, social upheaval, and other factors contribute to the growing orphan crisis in the region, leaving countless children bereft of the nurturing environment essential for their growth and development. Kids in any country are fundamental assets and the future of that very nation. It is the responsibility of society to provide sufficient opportunities to improve the physical, mental, social and moral growth as well as personality development and education (Abro, 2012). In this context, the establishment of SOS Children's Village Faisalabad emerges as a beacon of hope, offering a sanctuary for orphaned children to find solace, support, and a sense of belonging. Founded on the principle of "Save Our Soul," SOS Children's Village embodies the ethos of compassion and empowerment, providing a comprehensive range of services aimed at addressing the myriad needs of orphaned children. The mission of SOS Children's Village Faisalabad transcends mere provision of shelter; it encompasses a holistic approach to orphan care, encompassing education, healthcare, and psychosocial support. Within the confines of its nurturing environment, orphaned children are not only provided with basic necessities but are also afforded the opportunity to thrive and fulfill their potential.

At the core of SOS Children's Village Faisalabad's mission is the belief in the transformative power of education. Recognizing education as the cornerstone of empowerment, the institution has invested significantly in establishing formal schooling facilities, vocational training programs, and extracurricular activities to enrich the educational experience of orphaned children. Furthermore, SOS Children's Village Faisalabad places a strong emphasis on fostering social integration and emotional well-being among its residents. Through mentorship programs, counseling services, and community engagement initiatives, the institution endeavors to instill confidence, resilience, and a sense of belonging in orphaned children, empowering them to navigate life's challenges with dignity and determination. Against the backdrop of socioeconomic disparities and institutional neglect, SOS Children's Village Faisalabad stands as a beacon of hope, embodying the spirit of compassion, resilience, and collective responsibility. The most common reason for the separation of kids from parental care includes poverty, lack of access to basic services, abuse, neglect, disease, disabilities and emergencies (Bilson and Cox, 2007). As we delve deeper into the programs, methodologies, and impact of this remarkable institution, we gain invaluable insights into the transformative potential of dedicated care and intervention in the lives of orphaned children.

1.2. Problem Statement

Orphaned children face numerous challenges, including limited access to education and social support systems, which hinder their holistic development and future prospects. In the context of Faisalabad, Pakistan, where the orphan crisis is prevalent, addressing these challenges is imperative to ensure the well-being and empowerment of orphaned children. SOS Children's Village Faisalabad serves as a key institution dedicated to providing educational and social support to orphaned children in the region. However, despite its efforts, there remains a need to comprehensively understand the effectiveness of the support programs offered by SOS Children's Village Faisalabad and the challenges encountered in delivering these programs. By addressing these gaps in knowledge, this study aims to contribute to the enhancement of educational and social support for orphaned children in Faisalabad and beyond.

1.3. Significance of the study

The study of educational and social support programs provided by SOS Children's Village Faisalabad holds significant importance due to its potential impact on the lives of orphaned children in the region. By comprehensively understanding the effectiveness of these programs, the study offers valuable insights into how they contribute to the educational attainment, social integration, and overall well-being of orphaned children. Through empirical evidence and firsthand accounts from both children and staff, the study enriches the existing body of literature on orphan care and support programs, particularly in the context of developing countries like Pakistan. Moreover, the findings of the study have important policy implications, informing policymakers and stakeholders about best practices and areas for improvement in orphan care initiatives. This knowledge can guide the development and implementation of policies aimed at enhancing support services for vulnerable youth, ultimately leading to improved outcomes and opportunities for orphaned children in Faisalabad and beyond. Furthermore, by highlighting the work of SOS Children's Village Faisalabad and its impact on the local community, the study fosters awareness and engagement among community members, promoting collaboration, resource mobilization, and advocacy efforts for orphaned children. Lastly, the study's findings and recommendations have relevance beyond the specific context of Faisalabad, contributing to global discussions on orphan care and support programs and facilitating cross-cultural exchange of knowledge and best practices to improve the lives of orphaned children worldwide.

1.2.1. Research Objectives:

- To identify and describe the educational support programs offered by SOS Children's Village Faisalabad, including formal schooling facilities, tutoring services, vocational training, and extracurricular activities.
- To assess the perceptions of orphaned children regarding the educational and social support provided by SOS Children's Village Faisalabad, including their satisfaction levels, perceived benefits, and areas for improvement.
- To explore the challenges faced by SOS Children's Village Faisalabad in delivering educational and social support to orphaned children, including financial constraints, staff turnover, and societal stigma, and to investigate the strategies employed by the institution to address these challenges.

1.2.2. Research Questions:

2. What are the key educational support programs implemented by SOS Children's Village Faisalabad for orphaned children?
3. How do orphaned children perceive the educational and social support provided by SOS Children's Village Faisalabad?
4. What are the challenges faced by SOS Children's Village Faisalabad in delivering educational and social support to orphaned children, and how are these challenges addressed?

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

According to Campbell. B (2006), education plays a significant role in human life regarding to build their personality, career and mental growth. Education is the best tool for facing any up and down situation through the whole life. We can not only improve our personal life by education but also can bring an amazing positive change in society or nation. To provide education among people, society has declared some places as home to education like Schools and Colleges where some pattern are followed in procedural manner to offer quality education for the aspiring students. Education is the only medium by which you can win this world. The great personalities till now have achieved big position in life just because of their hard work and education. Education makes us polite, humble, kind, civilized and responsible human being. An educated person can easily influence anyone by his intelligence.

As Quran says

(Their bearings) on this life and the Hereafter. They ask thee concerning orphans. Say: "The best thing to do is what is for their good; if ye mix their affairs with yours, they are your brethren; but Allah knows the man who means mischief from the man who means good. And if Allah had wished, He could have put you into difficulties: He is indeed Exalted in Power, Wise." (Surah Al-Baqara, 220)

UNICEF (2008) and global partners define an orphan as a child under 18 years of age who has lost one or both parents to any cause of death. By this definition, there were nearly 140 million orphans globally in 2015, including 61 million in Asia, 52 million in Africa, 10 million in Latin America and the Caribbean, and 7.3 million in Eastern Europe and Central Asia. This large figure represents not only children who have lost both parents, but also those who have lost a father but have a surviving mother or have lost their mother but have a surviving father. Of the nearly 140 million children classified as orphans, 15.1 million have lost both parents. Evidence clearly shows that the vast majority of orphans are living with a surviving parent grandparent, or other family member. 95 per cent of all orphans are over the age of five. This definition contrasts with concepts of orphan in many industrialized countries, where a child must have lost both parents to qualify as an orphan. UNICEF and numerous international organizations adopted the broader definition of orphan in the mid-1990s as the AIDS pandemic began leading to the death of millions of parents worldwide, leaving an ever increasing number of children growing up without one or more parents. So the terminology of a 'single orphan' – the loss of one parent – and a 'double orphan' – the loss of both parents – was born to convey this growing crisis. However, this difference in terminology can have concrete implications for policies and programming for children. For example, UNICEF's 'orphan' statistic might be interpreted to mean that globally there are 140 million children in need of a new family, shelter, or care. This misunderstanding may then lead to responses that focus on providing care for individual children rather than supporting the families and communities that care for orphans and are in need of

support. In keeping with this and the agency's commitment to adapt to the evolving realities of the AIDS crisis, UNICEF commissioned an analysis of population household surveys across 36 countries. Designed to compare current conditions of orphans and non-orphans, the global analysis suggests we should further expand our scope, focusing less on the concept of orphan hood and more on a range of factors that render children vulnerable. These factors include the family's ownership of property, the poverty level of the household, the child's relationship to the head of the household, and the education level of the child's parents, if they are living. In UNICEF's experience, these are the elements that can help identify both children and their families – whether this term includes living parents, grandparents or other relatives – who have the greatest need for our support.

Lone and Ganesan (2016) examined the environmental effect on the development of orphan kids and their achievement. This study investigated the socio-economic status of orphans regarding the role of the orphanages. Al-Hilal English Medium trust in Pulwama District of Kashmir valley was selected as a population. Results of the study revealed that Al-Hilal English medium trust plays an important role in the life of orphans as the majority of the kids were satisfied with all the facilities. Al-Hilal English medium trust is considered as a major orphanage operating in Kashmir Valley which takes care of the necessities of orphan kids.

Magagula (2015) explored the role of kids' orphanage homes in the educational performance of primary school learners. This study was conducted in three schools and kids' home. The respondents in this study were six caregivers, six teachers and six learners. The responses were composed using in-depth interviews as an instrument. The major findings indicated that kids's homes can affect the performance negatively or positively. Positively in a sense, if homes provide enough time for kids to study and provide plenty of access to people and resources in support of their studies and negative in a sense that, if there are numerous educational barriers that the caregivers in the kids' home face daily when it comes to assisting the orphaned and vulnerable learners in their school work.

Rather and Margoob (2006) analyzed the available services and their effect on the psychological alteration of the orphan kids. High marks were associated with adverse living conditions, like poor housing setup, hard timetables poor recreation facilities weak nutrition and absence of modern educational facilities. These facts could verify seminal in planning for better rehabilitation modules for orphans, especially in the wake of their exponential enhance in the chronic conflict and disaster impact regions.

(Dwyer, 2016) highlighted that many kids leave home because of domestic abuse, neglect, and poverty only to suffer the brutal realities of living on the streets. They now lack clean water, proper shelter, a nutritional diet, have health concerns and are constantly exposed to illicit drugs, and communicable and sexually transmitted diseases. Additionally, street kids can be vulnerable to exploitation in the form of child labor, prostitution, and trafficking. These kids become especially vulnerable because they lack a support system that seeks to improve their education, health, and overall well-being.

Shackman and Reynolds (1997) gave a clearer picture of the multidimensional problems which children face in conflict situation. Children of war often show symptoms of severe psychological

trauma, sleeping disorders, and problem of their concentration, nightmares, withdrawal, aggression, fear of unexpected souls and movements clinging behavior, depression, inability to form close relation, bed-wetting and so on. These symptoms affect the way they relate to the world around them.

Cozolino (2002) mentioned in their research studies have consistently shown that parental loss in childhood and the absence of a warm, quality caretaker does effect depression in childhood and eventually in the adulthood. Melgosa (2011) explored that the stage of adolescence tends to be the most difficult one throughout the life cycle. Many boys and girls of this age seem to cause problems in the family, school and community. Erikson (1974) psychosocial theory investigated on adolescence stage shows that these children are faced with psychosocial crisis of identity vs. role confusion. They experiment with a variety of activities. It was therefore the main aim of this research to find out the adolescents' lifeworlds on school-based psychosocial support. Flank D, et.al (1996;97) were of opinion, children institutional care are extremely vulnerable to psychological problem and institutionalization in long term and in early childhood increases the likelihood that they will grow into psychologically impaired and economically unproductive adult.

“DAWN” newspapers (2012) reported that the number of orphan children being looked after by Pakistan Baitul Maal (PBM) has constantly been rising and presently 2,800 such children are being accommodated at its Sweet Homes established in different cities. “Last year, there were only 1,500 orphans,” said Pakistan Baitul Maal (PBM) Chairman Zamarud Khan while talking to reporters at a press conference here on Sunday. The PBM is financially supporting these poor children including their education, boarding, food, clothing and health care. Baitul Maal has brought these children to the federal capital to participate in a week-long grand gala being organised at the Sports Complex in connection with Pakistan Day on March 23. The mega event includes multiple activities like peace march, cultural shows, national songs and different games. Mr Khan said the parliamentarians, ambassadors, dignitaries and other people have been invited to spend some time with these children to encourage them and make them return to the mainstream of the society.

Skinner, 2004 stated that there exists a large number of ways to define orphans depending on the usage of the definition; epidemiologically, legal or as a social and cultural definition. The latter will vary between people and societies. Some people in Embu say that “in Embu we have no orphans”. People explained this with the existence of the extended family system and how this ensured that no child was ever left on its own. People did not refer to children that had lost 24 their parents as orphans, because these children still had caretakers and thus where not orphans by their definition. In addition to the usage of various age-groups when defining orphans, there is also the pattern of parental death; maternal, paternal or double orphans. All these different ways of defining orphans have program and policy implications and need to be thoroughly considered and fully understood before set into practice.

3. METHODOLOGY

The methodology employed in this study aimed to comprehensively assess the role of SOS Children's Village Faisalabad in enhancing educational and social support for orphaned children.

A mixed-method approach combining quantitative and qualitative research methodologies was utilized to gather a comprehensive understanding of the subject matter. The following outlines the key components of the methodology:

2.1. Sampling Strategy:

The study population comprised orphaned children residing in SOS Children's Village Faisalabad, as well as teachers and staff members involved in the administration and implementation of educational and social support programs. Moreover, purposive sampling was utilized to select the study population, ensuring representation from different age groups, genders, and lengths of residency in the village. Furthermore, a total of 127 respondents were included in the study, comprising 99 orphaned children and 28 teachers/staff members.

2.2.1. Data Collection Techniques:

Quantitative data were collected through structured questionnaires administered to orphaned children and teachers/staff members. The questionnaires were designed to elicit demographic information, perceptions of available facilities, and challenges faced by orphaned children. In addition, qualitative data were gathered through semi-structured interviews and observations conducted with orphaned children and teachers/staff members. These interviews and observations provided deeper insights into the experiences, attitudes, and perspectives of participants regarding educational and social support within SOS Children's Village Faisalabad.

2.3.1. Research Design:

A cross-sectional research design was employed to capture a snapshot of the educational and social support landscape within SOS Children's Village Faisalabad at a specific point in time. Moreover, descriptive statistics were used to analyze quantitative data, including frequency distributions and measures of central tendency. In addition, qualitative data were analyzed thematically, identifying recurring patterns, themes, and insights emerging from interviews and observations.

2.4.1. Data Analysis:

Quantitative data were analyzed using statistical software, such as SPSS, to generate descriptive statistics and identify trends and patterns. Furthermore, qualitative data were transcribed, coded, and thematically analyzed to identify key themes, categories, and subcategories relevant to the research objectives. By employing a mixed-method approach, this study sought to provide a comprehensive and nuanced understanding of the educational and social support landscape within SOS Children's Village Faisalabad, shedding light on the experiences, perceptions, and challenges faced by orphaned children and the individuals tasked with supporting them.

4. ANALYSIS

4.1. Educational Support Programs:

Within SOS Children's Village Faisalabad, educational support programs are central to the institution's mission of empowering orphaned children through knowledge and skills acquisition. These programs are designed to provide comprehensive educational opportunities that cater to the diverse needs and aspirations of the children under their care. Moreover, SOS Children's Village Faisalabad operates its own formal schooling facilities, providing orphaned children with access to quality education from primary through secondary levels. In addition, the curriculum is tailored to meet national educational standards while also incorporating elements that address the unique needs and backgrounds of orphaned children. Beside, qualified teachers and staff members are employed to deliver instruction and support students' academic progress.

Recognizing the importance of personalized support, SOS Children's Village Faisalabad offers tutoring and remedial classes for students who may require additional assistance in specific subjects. Furthermore, these classes are conducted by experienced educators who provide individualized attention and guidance to help students overcome academic challenges and excel in their studies. By having educational environmental facilities a child would get better education and have more and multiple choices and opportunities in the future to upgrade his socio-economic status; and come into a position for taking a charge on new social responsibilities in the community (NELA, 2008). In addition to traditional academic education, SOS Children's Village Faisalabad offers vocational training programs aimed at equipping orphaned children with practical skills for future employment and self-sufficiency. These programs cover a range of vocational fields, including carpentry, tailoring, computer literacy, and agricultural techniques, allowing students to explore their interests and talents. This subsection defines the education facilities provided by SOS village to the orphans with its descriptive statistics.

Table 1

Educational Facilities	Weighted Score	Mean	Std. Deviation	Rank
School has modern library	422	4.26	0.53	1
School has good and airy classrooms	414	4.18	0.64	2
Uniforms are provided	406	4.10	0.69	3
Mosque facility is there for religious education	403	4.07	0.75	4
Qaaris and Ulmas are available to facilitate children	403	4.07	0.92	5
School is divided into sections (juniors/boys/girls)	402	4.06	0.57	6
Each classroom has proper furniture, white/black boards, fans and other basic facilities	402	4.06	0.96	7
School has enough teachers for each subject	401	4.05	0.92	8
School has ICT gadgets and modern labs for modern learning	399	4.03	0.83	9
Extra curriculum activities are designed by the teachers	393	3.97	0.76	10
Teachers use computers/laptops, multimedia and labs for teaching	387	3.91	1.05	11
Teachers are kind and educated	379	3.83	0.95	12
School library has enough knowledgeable material according to the students' level	379	3.83	0.89	13
School books, copies and other accessories are provided on time	379	3.83	1.08	14
There is any complaint box in school	367	3.71	1.08	15
Teachers facilitate you as a teacher and a parent too	363	3.67	0.89	16
Educational trips are organized for better understanding	319	3.22	1.26	17

Beyond the classroom, SOS Children's Village Faisalabad places emphasis on holistic development through extracurricular activities such as sports, arts, and cultural events. These

activities provide opportunities for orphaned children to cultivate teamwork, leadership skills, and creativity while also fostering a sense of belonging and community within the village. Moreover, the institution offers various educational support services, including academic counseling, career guidance, and access to educational resources such as libraries and study materials. Trained counselors and mentors are available to provide emotional support and guidance to students, addressing any barriers to learning and facilitating their overall academic success. Through these comprehensive educational support programs, SOS Children's Village Faisalabad aims to empower orphaned children with the knowledge, skills, and confidence they need to build a brighter future for themselves. By fostering a supportive and nurturing learning environment, the institution instills a love for learning and a sense of hope in the hearts of orphaned children, enabling them to overcome adversity and achieve their full potential.

4.2.Social Support Initiatives:

In addition to providing educational opportunities, SOS Children's Village Faisalabad places a strong emphasis on fostering social integration, emotional well-being, and personal development among orphaned children. The social environment in which orphans live is not only reach from the care and support offered by caregivers, family members, friends, neighbors, teachers, health workers, and community members on an everyday basis but also expands to those offered by specialized psychological and social aids (Mushunje MT, 2006). Through a variety of initiatives and programs, the institution strives to create a supportive and nurturing environment where children can thrive socially and emotionally. SOS Children's Village Faisalabad implements mentorship programs that pair orphaned children with caring adult mentors from the community. Furthermore, mentors serve as positive role models, offering guidance, encouragement, and support to children as they navigate life's challenges and transitions. And, these mentorship relationships help foster a sense of belonging, confidence, and personal growth among orphaned children, empowering them to reach their full potential. This subsection defines the social environment provided by SOS village to the orphans with its descriptive statistics.

Table 2

Social Environment Facilities	Weighted Score	Mean	Std. Deviation	Rank
Are you satisfied with the interaction of SOS fellows	420	4.24	0.62	1
Are you satisfied with the standard of living	410	4.14	0.71	2
Are you satisfied with the cooperation between children	407	4.11	0.67	3
Are you satisfied with the social environment of SOS	405	4.09	0.61	4
Are you satisfied with the interaction of staff of SOS	387	3.91	0.61	5
Are you satisfied with the interaction of SOS mothers	383	3.87	0.75	6
Are you satisfied with the interaction of SOS teachers	380	3.84	0.60	7

The social environment in which orphans live is not only reach from the care and support offered by caregivers, family members, friends, neighbors, teachers, health workers, and community members on an everyday basis but also expands to those offered by specialized psychological and social aids (Mushunje MT, 2006).

Trained counselors are available to provide emotional support, guidance, and counseling to orphaned children who may be experiencing trauma, grief, or other psychological challenges. Counseling sessions offer a safe space for children to express their feelings, process their

experiences, and develop coping strategies for managing stress and adversity. This subsection defines the barriers and challenges faced by orphan provided by SOS village to the teacher / staff with its descriptive statistics.

Table 3

Barrier and Challenges Faced by Orphans	Weighted Score	Mean	Std. Deviation	Rank
Government neglects the orphan children	106	3.78	0.93	1
Lack of funding for orphans in Government policies	91	3.26	0.98	2
An orphan's negative behavior affects his/her educational and societal growth	77	2.74	1.40	3
The orphans have to face many problems due to less financial support	65	2.33	1.04	4
Psychological problems and mental sickness is a hurdle	65	2.33	1.52	5
Less financial support is a hindrance	60	2.15	0.99	6
Lack of donors is a barrier for orphan's educational and societal growth	56	2.00	0.78	7
No proper policies are made and applied for orphan's support	52	1.85	0.53	8

By addressing the emotional needs of orphaned children, SOS Children's Village Faisalabad helps promote mental health and resilience, enabling children to thrive despite their circumstances. SOS Children's Village Faisalabad organizes a variety of recreational activities and outings for children, including sports, games, cultural events, and outdoor excursions. These activities provide opportunities for children to socialize, build friendships, and develop teamwork and leadership skills. Recreation also serves as a means of relaxation and enjoyment, allowing children to experience joy, laughter, and a sense of normalcy amidst their challenging circumstances. SOS Children's Village Faisalabad actively engages with the surrounding community to promote social inclusion and integration for orphaned children. Community events, volunteer opportunities, and partnerships with local organizations provide children with opportunities to interact with and contribute to the broader community. By fostering positive relationships and connections with the community, SOS Children's Village Faisalabad helps orphaned children feel valued, accepted, and supported within their social environment. Through these social support initiatives, SOS Children's Village Faisalabad aims to nurture the social and emotional well-being of orphaned children, providing them with the support, guidance, and opportunities they need to thrive and succeed in life. By addressing the holistic needs of children beyond their educational requirements, the institution creates a nurturing and empowering environment where every child has the opportunity to reach their full potential.

4.3. Impact and Success Stories:

The impact of SOS Children's Village Faisalabad extends far beyond its physical facilities; it resides in the transformed lives of orphaned children who have found hope, support, and a sense of belonging within its walls. Through its comprehensive educational and social support programs, the institution has made a profound difference in the lives of countless children, empowering them to overcome adversity and pursue their dreams. Many orphaned children who

have grown up in SOS Children's Village Faisalabad have achieved remarkable success in their academic endeavors. From excelling in national examinations to pursuing higher education and professional careers, these children have defied the odds and realized their full academic potential. Through the institution's educational support programs, children have gained the knowledge, skills, and confidence they need to succeed academically and pursue their aspirations.

Beyond academic achievements, SOS Children's Village Faisalabad has played a pivotal role in the personal development and growth of orphaned children. Through mentorship programs, counseling services, and recreational activities, children have developed essential life skills such as resilience, empathy, and leadership. Many children have overcome past traumas and adversity, emerging as confident, resilient individuals who are equipped to navigate life's challenges with grace and determination. Moreover, SOS Children's Village Faisalabad has fostered strong connections with the surrounding community, promoting social inclusion and integration for orphaned children. Through community engagement initiatives and partnerships with local organizations, children have had the opportunity to participate in community events, volunteer activities, and cultural exchanges. By forging positive relationships with neighbors, volunteers, and community members, children have felt valued, accepted, and supported within their broader social environment. It is a growing truth that a healthy body has a healthy mind and physical activity is important to evoke mental health and sustain physical health (Gorczyński and Faulkner 2010).

There are numerous success stories of orphaned children who have thrived under the care and support of SOS Children's Village Faisalabad. From becoming successful professionals to giving back to their communities as mentors and volunteers, these children have gone on to lead fulfilling and meaningful lives. Their stories serve as testament to the transformative impact of SOS Children's Village Faisalabad, inspiring hope and optimism for the future of orphaned children everywhere. These impact stories and success stories exemplify the profound difference that SOS Children's Village Faisalabad has made in the lives of orphaned children, offering them a second chance at a brighter future. Through its unwavering commitment to education, support, and empowerment, the institution has not only transformed individual lives but also enriched the fabric of the community, leaving a lasting legacy of hope, resilience, and compassion.

5. CONCLUSION:

The case study of SOS Children's Village Faisalabad offers valuable insights into the transformative impact of dedicated care and support on the lives of orphaned children. Through a comprehensive examination of educational and social support programs, as well as firsthand accounts from residents and staff, several key findings and insights have emerged. Firstly, SOS Children's Village Faisalabad has been instrumental in providing orphaned children with access to quality education, vocational training, and personal development opportunities. The institution's holistic approach to education, coupled with its emphasis on social integration and emotional well-being, has enabled children to thrive academically, socially, and emotionally. Success stories abound, demonstrating the remarkable resilience and potential of orphaned children when provided with the necessary support and opportunities.

Moreover, the research underscores the broader implications of SOS Children's Village Faisalabad's model for orphan care and support programs globally. By prioritizing the holistic

development of children and fostering strong connections with the community, the institution serves as a beacon of hope and inspiration for similar initiatives around the world. The success of SOS Children's Village Faisalabad highlights the importance of investing in comprehensive, community-based approaches to orphan care, which prioritize education, support, and empowerment. Moving forward, policymakers, NGOs, and other stakeholders can draw upon the lessons learned from SOS Children's Village Faisalabad to further enhance educational and social support for orphaned children. Recommendations include: Policymakers should prioritize investment in education for orphaned children, ensuring access to quality schooling, vocational training, and educational support services. NGOs and organizations working with orphaned children should adopt a holistic approach to support, addressing not only educational needs but also social, emotional, and developmental aspects.

Stakeholders should foster strong connections between orphaned children and the broader community, promoting social inclusion, integration, and support networks. Staff members and caregivers working with orphaned children should receive adequate training and support to effectively meet the diverse needs of children under their care. Continued research and evaluation of orphan care programs are essential to identify best practices, address challenges, and improve outcomes for orphaned children globally. By implementing these recommendations and drawing upon the insights gained from SOS Children's Village Faisalabad, stakeholders can work together to create a more inclusive, supportive, and empowering environment for orphaned children worldwide, ensuring that every child has the opportunity to reach their full potential and lead fulfilling lives.

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